

A STUDY ON MENTAL HEALTH OF UNEMPLOYED GRADUATES DURING THE PANDEMIC IN BENGALURU

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Abstract: *The purpose of this research is to make a review of the mental health of the unemployed graduates during the pandemic in Bangalore. There are so many causes which affect mental health like stress, anxiety, depression, etc. due to unemployment. This study is to understand the struggles they have faced and to know how much confidence they had when they were facing the difficulties during the pandemic. The purpose of this study was to provide a review of current research about mental health of youths. The study used 50 respondents for the purpose of getting feedback from the unemployed graduates during the pandemic. The study says that most of the respondents felt stress due to financial difficulties they have faced during the pandemic are the main cause of their poor mental health. Even though they have faced so many mental health problems they had great confidence in them.*

Key words: Anxiety, confidence level, financial difficulties, mental health, stress level.

Introduction

Unemployment has a detrimental impact on mental health, not having a job and actively seeking work has consistently been found to have a negative impact on a range of mental health outcomes especially during pandemic (covid19). There are several mechanisms by which unemployment could harm health through stress and reduced self-esteem arising from the loss of confidence because of financial hardship, insecurity and reduced future earnings potential, leaving people in stress. Unemployment is a frightening problem. The economy is completely dependent on the youth employment generation in particular rather it holds the supremacy of the development of the country. Recent years India, especially in Bengaluru is facing a major challenge of unemployment due to lack of skill training, as well as skill education. Due to unemployment many youths are losing their confidence level and it causes a reduction in one's mental health. It leads to depression and decreased self-esteem the study used 50 respondents for the purpose to get feedback on their mental health during pandemic. The main cause of their poor mental health was financial difficulties they have faced has been found in the research.

Statement of the Problem

Nowadays many graduates are facing mental health problems like stress, anxiety, depression, etc. Unemployment after graduation is one of the main causes for all the above mental health problems. Especially during the pandemic, the stress level of the graduates has been increased due to shortage of employment opportunities.

Importance of the study

The study analysis on analysis on unemployed graduates during the pandemic in Bangalore. An attempt has been made by the researcher to know the causes for poor mental health, financial difficulties, and the confidence level of the respondents. The findings of the study will ultimately reveal why they were suffering from poor mental health.

Objectives of the study

The objective of study are as follows

- To know the mental stress and financial difficulties faced by unemployed graduates
- To find the confidence level of unemployed graduates while facing difficulties during the pandemic

Research methodology

Research methodology is a systematic way to solve the research problem. This study was made on unemployed graduates during the pandemic in Bangalore. The questionnaires include questions related to socio-economic profile of unemployed graduates and things that made them stressed, financial difficulties they have faced and confidence level of the respondents.

Sampling design

To analyse mental health of unemployed graduates primary data has been collected through google form. 50 respondents were chosen among the population of unemployed graduates in Bangalore.

Limitations of the study

The following are the Limitations of the study

- This study is limited to 50 respondents only
- This study is limited to Bangalore only
- Time duration of study from December 2021 to January 2022

Findings and results

The present study was to examine the mental health of unemployed graduates. Unemployed people are very likely to experience psychological tension, mainly depression and anxiety,

which negatively affects their health, their family security and society ability in general.

Mental stress and financial difficulties faced by unemployed graduates

While the pandemic has undoubtedly increased worries about financial security, many graduates have found themselves facing financial challenges. Being unemployed can lead to depression, low self-esteem, anxiety, and other mental health issues. Especially if an individual truly wants a job but fine employment. Tension can occur, causing stress and strain on the body. High unemployment rate can be attributed to decreasing confidence level and it leads to problems of financial needs. The study reveals that people at both high-income and low-income levels suffered financial difficulties due to covid-19.

Mental stress of unemployed graduates

Stress is a condition of mental pressure for particular individuals facing problems from environment and social well-being which leads to so many diseases. Being unemployed for a long period of time in youths has been correlated to decrease happiness, depression and other mental health issues. Unemployed graduates also report more isolation from their community. Youths who are neither working nor studying do not have opportunities. To learn and improve their skills. Due to high stress youth are losing their thinking capacity and losing their confidence level, it causes damage to the lives of graduates. So they should enhance their stress management abilities so as to live a healthy life after entering the society.

Table 1

Mental stress of unemployed graduates during pandemic

Mental stress	Never	Almost never	Once in a while	Often	Very often	Total
Concentration level	10	10	14	11	5	50
Lose sleep	5	12	12	10	11	50
Overwhelmed and a stressed	6	8	9	17	10	50
normal daily activity	3	3	15	11	11	50
Unhappy depressed	10	9	3	10	18	50
Daily life	26	3	10	11	Nil	50

The table 1 conclude that the mental stress of unemployed graduates have been greatly affected by unemployment most of the respondents are stressed because of their family financial situations, how the society will treat them and other causes .out of 50 respondents majority of them were not able to concentrate well to be particular out of 50 respondents 40

of them were stressed due to unemployment and not able to concentrate well. out of 50 at least 45 of them were not able to sleep properly because of the stress which was caused by unemployment.46 of them were struggling from stress at least once in a while, because of the stress most of them were unhappy or depressed during the pandemic and they were not able to enjoy their daily life.

Financial difficulties of unemployed graduates during pandemic

The study says that most of the respondents felt stress due to financial difficulties during the pandemic are the main cause of their poor mental health. So many graduates were not able to find a job and are having a hard time that it has increased their financial stress. Youths are finding themselves taking on more debt, and struggling to pay off loans and housing rent.

Table 2

Financial difficulties of unemployed graduates

Financial difficulties	No of respondents	Percentage
Loans	10	20%
personal debt	5	10%
basic needs\daily expenses	10	20%
other expenses	5	10%
all of the above	20	40%
total	50	100%

The above table 2 shows what kind of financial difficulties have been faced by unemployed graduates.by looking at the table we can tell 20% of the respondents were suffering from not able to repay the loans or interest for their loans , 10% of them were suffering from personal debt, 20% them were not able to pay their daily expenses which includes food expenses, medical expenses, rent for the house,etc.10% of them were suffering from other expenses and 20% them suffering from loan, personal debt, daily expenses, and other expenses

Confidence level of unemployed graduates during pandemic

Confidence helps us feel ready for life's experiences. When we are confident, we are more likely to move forward with people and opportunities. If things don't work out first confidence helps us to try again. It's the opposite when the confidence is low. Confidence gives us the skills and coping methods to handle setbacks and failures. Being more confident is not just some trivial goal or resolution.it is truly an important part of our lives.

Table 3 Confidence level of unemployed graduates

Confidence level	No of respondents	Percentage
Playing a useful role	8	16%
Decision making	5	10%
Confidence level	10	20%
Continuous job rejection	15	30%
Positive and energetic	12	24%

The above table 3 shows how confidence the respondents were during the pandemic.16% of the respondents felt they were playing a useful role in life, only 10% of the respondents were able to make the decisions relating to their life or whatever.20% of the respondents were confident about them .30% of the respondents were lost their confidence due to continuous job rejections and 24% of the respondents were positive and energetic during the pandemic.

Conclusion

Study on mental health of unemployed graduates during the pandemic is that this pandemic has affected the life of graduates both financially and mentally. The pandemic had changed the dynamics of the employment of every place. The job opportunities have decreased, and competition has increased. Graduates who used to get jobs easily are not able to get job now because of the situation making them lose confidence and push them into depression. During our research, we met many graduates who had to consult a psychiatrist because of mental health, and they were graduates who did not lose confidence and were still trying for the jobs. I can conclude that this pandemic had taken the test of graduate's mental health and most of them fought against it bravely. The government and some responsible authorities should take steps and help the graduates with their current situation by helping them get jobs or offering help financially and provide or guide them about mental health.

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